

This work was carried out in whole or in part within the framework of the NOMATEN Centre of Excellence, supported from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 857470) and from the European Regional Development Fund via the Foundation for Polish Science International Research Agenda PLUS program (Grant No. MAB PLUS/2018/8), and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education's initiative "Support for the Activities of Centers of Excellence Established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 Program" (agreement no. MEiN/2023/DIR/3795).

The version of record of this article, first published in Journal of Nuclear Materials, Volume 615, September 2025, 155994, on 19 June 2025, is available online at Publisher's website:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.155994>

This manuscript version is made available under CC BY 4.0 license.

Effect of Zr addition on the structure, nanomechanical properties, and helium irradiation behavior of the novel MoTaTiV body-centered cubic concentrated solid solution alloy

Damian Kalita^{a,*}, Katarzyna Mulewska^a, Iwona Józwick^a, Yanwen Zhang^{b,c}, Łukasz Kurpaska^a, Philip D. Rack^c, William J. Weber^c, Jacek Jagielski^a

^a NOMATEN Centre of Excellence, National Centre for Nuclear Research, A. Soltana 7 St., Otwock, 05-400, Poland

^b Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Queen's University, Kingston, Ontario, K7L 3N6, Canada

^c Department of Materials Science & Engineering, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, TN, 37996, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Concentrated solid solution alloys
High entropy alloys
Ion irradiation
Radiation damage
He bubbles
Nuclear materials

ABSTRACT

The rapidly developing technology of fusion reactors requires the development of new materials with enhanced radiation resistance. In this study, two new equimolar concentrated solid solution alloys (CSAs), MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr, designed for nuclear applications, were synthesized using magnetron sputtering. The MoTaTiV alloy exhibited a columnar microstructure, characteristic for materials produced via magnetron sputtering, and a body-centered cubic (BCC) structure. The addition of Zr to form the quinary MoTaTiVZr alloy led to the formation of an amorphous phase due to increased lattice distortion caused by the introduction of Zr into the crystal structure of the base alloy. To evaluate the irradiation resistance of the synthesized alloys, the materials were irradiated with 200 keV He⁺ ions. In the case of MoTaTiV, helium bubble formation was initially observed primarily at column boundaries, which serve as preferential nucleation sites. However, at a fluence of 5×10^{16} cm⁻², bubbles were also detected within the matrix. For the MoTaTiVZr alloy, due to its amorphous structure, bubbles were uniformly distributed throughout the matrix. Despite these differences in He accumulation behavior, the bubbles in the MoTaTiVZr CSA were slightly smaller, indicating that increasing lattice distortion inhibits bubble growth. Furthermore, the absence of radiation-induced hardening in both materials suggests a high intrinsic resistance to radiation damage.

1. Introduction

The development of nuclear fusion technology drives the search for new irradiation-resistant plasma facing materials (PFMs) for critical components of the future reactors, such as the divertor. Currently, research in this field is focused on two main aspects: improving the performance of existing materials, mainly tungsten, or exploring new materials [1,2]. Among the latter group, concentrated solid solution alloys (CSAs) appear to be one of the most widely studied material classes nowadays [3]. CSAs represent a novel class of metallic alloys characterized by the presence of multiple elements at significant concentration (typically >5 at. %) and often in near-equimolar proportions. Particular examples of these alloys include high-entropy alloys (HEAs), which consist of at least five near-equimolar, and medium-entropy

alloys (MEAs), which typically contain 3 – 4 various elements [4,5].

In nuclear fusion, several factors affect the performance of structural materials. These include, among others, neutron (14.1 MeV) and He⁺ ion (3.5 MeV) irradiation, originating from the deuterium-tritium fusion (DTF) reaction, plasma exposure, and high operation temperatures (>1073 K) [6]. Under such conditions, tungsten, which is currently considered as a material for PFCs, is susceptible to irradiation hardening [7]. This susceptibility is related to its high tendency to form defects in the form of dislocation loops, even at low displacement per atom (dpa) values, such as 0.01 dpa [8,9]. Therefore, in recent years, research efforts have focused on finding materials with improved irradiation resistance [10]. From the perspective of fusion reactor materials, body-centered cubic (BCC) CSAs containing refractory elements appear to be the most promising candidates [2]. The interest in CSA-type alloys

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Damian.Kalita@ncbj.gov.pl (D. Kalita).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.155994>

Received 28 February 2025; Received in revised form 18 May 2025; Accepted 18 June 2025

Available online 19 June 2025

0022-3115/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

in this context stems from their unique point defect kinetics under irradiation. Due to their significant chemical complexity and the resulting lattice strain, the accumulation of radiation-induced defects, such as dislocation loops and voids, is considerably lower than in conventional materials used in the nuclear industry [11,12]. This is attributed to the increased probability of point defect recombination, resulting from their similar mobilities [13]. Consequently, this leads to a substantial reduction in the degradation of mechanical properties in irradiation environments, potentially extending the materials' operational lifespan. In contrast, in pure W, interstitials exhibit significantly higher mobility compared to vacancies, leading to a lower recombination rate and the formation of extensive dislocation loops [14].

Another factor that significantly affects the performance of materials used in fusion technology arises from He-irradiation. He atoms implanted into the crystal structure of the material lead to the formation of He bubbles, which can degrade the performance of structural materials due to swelling and grain boundary embrittlement [15,16]. Furthermore, He-irradiation can lead to other dangerous phenomena, such as surface erosion and fuzz formation [17,18]. Taking this into consideration, a comprehensive understanding of the formation and evolution mechanisms of the defects formed during the He-irradiation in refractory CSAs is crucial for their further development.

The main aim of this article is to understand how the chemical complexity of CSAs influences He-ion irradiation behavior. For this purpose, two new equimolar refractory CSAs, quaternary MoTaTiV and quinary MoTaTiVZr alloys, were synthesized using the magnetron sputtering technique. The MoTaTiV alloy was selected as the starting point based on several considerations. Previous modeling studies have indicated that it should exhibit a single-phase structure, possess enhanced mechanical properties at elevated temperatures, and have a high melting point, making it a promising candidate for high-temperature applications [19,20]. However, these predictions have not yet been confirmed experimentally. Additionally, the MoTaTiV compositionally complex solid solution alloy (CSA) is characterized by relatively low lattice distortion, which can be significantly increased by the addition of Zr without altering the crystal structure [21]. This makes the system an excellent candidate for studying the effect of lattice distortion on the irradiation behavior of BCC—CSAs. In this context, Zr was chosen due to its large atomic radius, which can introduce significant lattice distortions [11]. This study systematically investigates the structure of equimolar MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr alloys, their nano-mechanical properties, and defect accumulation under He⁺ ion irradiation.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material fabrication and He-irradiation

The studied MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr CSAs were prepared using the magnetron sputtering in the form of thin layer on the Si substrate. The deposition process was carried out at room temperature (RT) with a target power of 200 W (445 V) for a duration of about 2.5 h, utilizing the AJA International ATC 2400-V magnetron sputtering system. During the process, the substrate was rotated to achieve a uniform film thickness. For additional details about the fabrication procedure, refer to [22].

After deposition, the layers were subjected to 200 keV He⁺-ion irradiation using a Danfysik Research Ion Implanter at the Ion Beam Materials Laboratory of Los Alamos National Laboratory. The process was carried out at room temperature (RT) with a beam flux of $4.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Two different fluences, $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, were applied. The irradiation was performed in a vacuum with a pressure of less than 5×10^{-7} Torr. Fig. 1 shows the damage and He accumulation profiles after the He-irradiation with the fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, calculated using the Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) software in Full Cascade mode [23]. The following displacement energies were used for the elements: Mo – 65 eV, Ta – 90 eV, Ti – 30 eV, V – 57 eV, and Zr – 40 eV [24]. The theoretical densities of 9.32 g/cm³ and 8.76 g/cm³ were applied for MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr, respectively. The damage levels of 1.18 and 1.38 dpa (displacement per atom) at a depth of approximately 500 nm were obtained for MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr, respectively. The peak concentration of implanted He atoms was found at a depth of 550 nm. In both cases, the calculations showed that the maximum concentration of He reached about 2.8 at. %. For better clarity, Fig. 1 shows profiles only for the higher fluence used ($5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$); however, Table 1 summarizes the values for both applied irradiation conditions.

Table 1

The damage levels and He concentration at the peak of the He-irradiated materials calculated using the SRIM software.

Fluence	MoTaTiV		MoTaTiVZr	
	Damage [dpa]	He concentration [at. %]	Damage [dpa]	He concentration [at. %]
$1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	0.24	0.56	0.28	0.59
$5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	1.18	2.82	1.38	2.94

Fig. 1. Accumulated damage (black lines) and He content (red lines) in MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr CSAs, after the He-irradiation with the fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, as a function of layer depth calculated using the SRIM software.

2.2. Materials characterization

The surface morphology of the as-deposited layers was examined using a ThermoFisher Scientific Helios 5 UX dual-beam scanning electron microscope (SEM). More detailed microstructural analysis was performed with a JEOL JEM-F200 transmission electron microscope (TEM), equipped with a JEOL dual SDD energy dispersive X-ray (EDS) system. Cross-sectional samples for TEM investigations were prepared using the focused ion beam (FIB) lift-out method. To minimize the occurrence of Ga-ion-induced defects, sample polishing was carried out with progressively decreased ion beam voltage, finishing at 2 kV. Final polishing of the TEM foils was performed using the Gatan PIPS II Precision Ion Polishing System with Ar⁺ ions at energies of 2 keV and 500 eV. The final cross-section width of the samples for observation was in the range of 50–60 nm.

The nanomechanical response of the material was measured using a NanoTest Vantage System (MicroMaterials Ltd.) equipped with a cube corner diamond indenter tip. This type of indenter provides more accurate hardness values in thin layers. Before testing, the diamond area function (DAF) of the indenter was calibrated using fused silica. Measurements were conducted in single-force mode with applied loads ranging from 0.25 mN to 5 mN, resulting in a deformation range of approximately 20–370 nm. Twenty tests were conducted for each load, with an indent spacing of 20 μm . Nanohardness values were determined from nanoindentation load–displacement (L-D) curves using the Oliver and Pharr method [25].

3. Results

3.1. Microstructural investigation

Fig. 2 presents the SEM micrographs of the surface morphology of the as-deposited MoTaTiV (Fig. 2a) and MoTaTiVZr (Fig. 2b) layers. Nanometric tetrahedral crystals are visible on the surface of the MoTaTiV layer, with an average size of approximately 50 nm. In contrast, the surface of the MoTaTiVZr layer appears relatively flat. This behavior results from the amorphous nature of the layer, which is discussed in more detail in the following sections. Similar effect has also been observed in other studies focusing on amorphous films produced by sputtering techniques, e.g. [26]. Nonetheless, in both cases, the deposited layers are uniform and free from extensive surface defects.

For a more detailed study of the deposited layers, TEM technique was applied. Fig. 3 presents the cross-sectional bright-field (BF) TEM images of the investigated CSAs. The studies revealed that MoTaTiV exhibits a densely packed V-shaped columnar microstructure, with columns elongated in the direction of layer growth and a thickness ranging from 50 to 100 nm. Their tops correspond to tetrahedral grains visible in the SEM images. The selected area diffraction (SAED) pattern obtained from

a group of columns (Fig. 3c) corresponds to a single body-centered cubic (BCC) structure, with no signs of secondary reflections indicative of other phases. In contrast, the SAED pattern obtained for the MoTaTiVZr layer (Fig. 3d) exhibits an amorphous character. However, minor spots corresponding to the BCC phase are also observed. Although the MoTaTiVZr layer primarily contains an amorphous structure after deposition by magnetron sputtering, individual crystalline islands with a well-defined BCC structure can be observed, as shown in Fig. 4.

The EDS elemental mapping (Fig. 5) indicates that both layers exhibit a uniform distribution of all alloying elements, with no evidence of segregation or the occurrence of secondary phases. The fine, perpendicular to the sample surface, variations in the distribution of elements in the MoTaTiVZr alloy resulted from changes in the sample thickness. The average composition of the alloying elements in the materials is close to equimolar, as shown in Table 2, with slight enrichment of Ta in the case of the MoTaTiV CSA and enrichment of Ta and Mo along with a depletion of Zr in the case of MoTaTiVZr.

3.2. Nanomechanical properties

Fig. 6 shows the nanohardness profiles for the investigated CSAs layers, measured via nanoindentation. The measurements were carried out at depths ranging from approximately 25 nm to 350 nm to reflect the whole thickness of the studied layers. In the case of the as-deposited MoTaTiV alloy the hardness of the layer slightly varies in the range 11–12 GPa, which may be associated with the highly developed surface morphology of the layer, as revealed from Fig. 2. However, after the initial indentation depth, the hardness stabilizes at the values of about 11 GPa. Interestingly, virtually no change in the hardness-depth curve is observed comparing the as-deposited and the He-irradiated (fluence $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) samples. This indicates that the material is not subjected to irradiation-hardening under the irradiation conditions applied within this work.

In the case of the MoTaTiVZr layer, the hardness profile for the as-deposited layer exhibits a more constant hardness-depth trend. Although the layer exhibited amorphous characteristics, as shown in Fig. 3, the hardness reached approximately 7 GPa. An increase in hardness can be observed at the end of the profile, for indentation depths greater than 300 nm, which is likely associated with the influence of the Si substrate. This effect was not visible in the case of the MoTaTiV layer, as it was slightly thicker compared to the MoTaTiVZr layer - 1300 nm and 700 nm, respectively, and its hardness was closer to the value of Si (~ 13 GPa). For the irradiated layer, the hardness values are slightly higher compared to the as-deposited sample. However, in this case, the profile did not exhibit the characteristic initial hardness increase typically observed in ion-irradiated materials. Instead, the hardness of the ion-irradiated sample remains consistently higher by a nearly constant value, regardless of the contact depth. This may not be directly related to

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of the surface morphology of MoTaTiV (a) and MoTaTiVZr (b) layers.

Fig. 3. BF/TEM micrographs of the as-deposited MoTaTiV (a) and MoTaTiVZr (b) layers, with the corresponding SAED patterns (c,d).

irradiation defects formed during irradiation but rather to an increase in the crystallinity of the sample, as observed for the ion-irradiated sample - see Fig. 8.

3.3. He-irradiation behavior

Fig. 7 presents over-focused TEM micrographs of the MoTaTiV CSA following He irradiation. Under these imaging conditions, the He bubbles appear as dark features. The micrographs were acquired from a depth ranging from 500 to 600 nm beneath the surface, corresponding to the simulated maximum concentration of the implanted He atoms, as observed from Fig. 1. At the lower fluence ($1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), He bubbles are predominantly located along the column boundaries. In this case, the bubbles are present in the form of channels along the grain boundaries rather than as isolated bubbles (Fig. 7b). Only individual bubbles are observed within the MoTaTiV matrix. As the fluence increases to $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the accumulation of bubbles at the column boundaries becomes more pronounced, forming larger channels. However, as observed in Fig. 7d, at this fluence level, a higher density of bubbles can also be present within the columns. These bubbles exhibit nanometric sizes, with an average diameter of $0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$, and are homogeneously

distributed throughout the matrix.

The addition of Zr to the initial quaternary MoTaTiV CSA significantly influenced the material's structure, as described in detail in Section 3.1. Consequently, it also affected the He accumulation behavior. As shown in Fig. 8, the presence of He bubbles within the matrix of the alloy is observed even at the lower fluence of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. As illustrated from Fig. 8b, at this stage the nanometric bubbles are uniformly distributed within the matrix, with no occurrence larger agglomerates. This phenomenon is related to the lack of preferential nucleation sites for He bubbles, such as column boundaries present in the MoTaTiV layer. Their average size at this fluence reached $0.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ nm}$. With increasing He ion fluence up to $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, no notable changes in the distribution of bubbles are observed, as revealed in Fig. 8d. However, a slight increase in bubble size, from $0.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ nm}$ to $0.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$, can be detected. The summary of the calculated bubble sizes in relation to the material and He-ion fluence is presented in Table 3.

For a better understanding of how He-ion irradiation affected the phase composition of the irradiated samples, the SAED patterns of the He-irradiated samples with a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ are shown in Fig. 9. No visible changes in the microstructure or crystal structure of

Fig. 4. HRTEM image of the as-deposited MoTaTiVZr layer with the corresponding FFT patterns.

Fig. 5. Cross-sectional STEM images of the MoTaTiV (a) and MoTaTiVZr (b) layers with the corresponding EDS elemental maps.

Table 2

Average chemical composition of the as-deposited MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr layers, measured using the EDS technique.

Alloy	Elemental composition [at. %]				
	Mo	Ta	Ti	V	Zr
MoTaTiV	24 ± 1	27 ± 1	24 ± 1	24 ± 1	-
MoTaTiVZr	22 ± 1	23 ± 1	20 ± 1	19 ± 1	17 ± 1

MoTaTiV were observed, as evidenced in Fig. 9a,c. Similar to the as-deposited sample, it exhibits a single-phase BCC structure, with no diffraction spots corresponding to secondary phases. However, when comparing the SAED patterns acquired for MoTaTiVZr before (Fig. 3d) and after irradiation (Fig. 9d), a more pronounced diffraction rings can be observed, suggesting an increase in the fraction of the BCC crystalline

structure. Nevertheless, the characteristic halo corresponding to the presence of an amorphous phase remains visible in the SAED pattern. This indicates that the amorphous MoTaTiVZr layer may undergo partial crystallization during ion irradiation. The acceleration of the recrystallization process due to irradiation has previously been reported for various amorphous materials, such as Zr-Cu alloys [27]. This phenomenon is attributed to enhanced diffusion within the amorphous phase, resulting from elastic collisions with highly energetic ions, as well as the formation of point defects during knock-out events, which act as diffusion carriers [28].

4. Discussion

PVD methods, such as magnetron sputtering, have recently become a common approach for the synthesis of new refractory CSAs for their

Fig. 6. Hardness profile of the pristine (V) and He⁺ irradiated (He) ($5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) MoTaTiV (a) and MoTaTiVZr (b) layers, measured using the nanoindentation.

initial evaluation in terms of structure, mechanical properties, and irradiation behavior [29]. This is mainly due to difficulties associated with other preparation methods, which typically involve melting the alloy constituents. Refractory CSA often contain elements with high melting points, such as W and Ta, or mixtures of metals with significant differences in melting points, e.g., W and Cr. In this case, the application of the PVD technique may provide a relatively straightforward method for fabricating new materials for research purposes [30]. Recently, several novel BCC—CSAs have been fabricated using this approach, for example WTaCrV [31,32], TaTiNbZr [33] or TaTiHfZr [34]. In such materials, a columnar microstructure is typically observed directly after deposition, similarly to the MoTaTiV alloy presented in this work (Fig. 3a). The MoTaTiV, as presented before, shows a well-defined BCC structure in the as-deposited state. However, when Zr was added to form the quinary MoTaTiVZr alloy, an amorphous structure was obtained. Guo et al. [35] reported that the atomic size difference is the critical parameter influenced the tendency of the multicomponent system to the formation of the amorphous phase. The formation of the amorphous phase was previously reported in the alloys with the lattice distortion parameter δ (Eq. (1)) higher than 6.5 % [36]:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i \left(1 - r_i / \sum_{j=1}^N c_j r_j\right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i}} \quad (1)$$

where c_i and r_i are the concentration and atomic radius of i th element, respectively. In the case of presented study, the addition of Zr to the initial equimolar MoTaTiV CSA significantly increased δ from 4.1 % to 6.8 %. This is in good agreement with the criteria proposed by Guo et al. [36]. The significant increase of δ for MoTaTiVZr is attributed to the relatively large atomic radius of Zr (1.60 Å) compared to the other constituents: Mo (1.36 Å), Ta (1.43 Å), Ti (1.46 Å), and V (1.32 Å) [35]. The occurrence of the amorphous phase was also observed in other BCC—CSAs containing elements with large differences in atomic radii, e.g., $\text{W}_{24}\text{Ta}_{40}\text{Cr}_{18}\text{V}_5\text{Hf}_{13}$ ($\delta=6.9\%$) [37]. However, it should be noted that PVD methods, such as magnetron sputtering, are highly non-equilibrium processes, which means that the studied MoTaTiVZr alloy, when fabricated by other processes, such as casting, may exhibit a crystalline structure. This is related to the high cooling rates occurring during the magnetron sputtering process, which have been reported to reach magnitudes of up to 10^{11} K/s [38].

In order to study the mechanical properties of these newly fabricated

CSAs, nanohardness measurements were carried out. Previous studies have demonstrated the applicability of this method in research on radiation hardening induced by ion irradiation [39,40]. The materials exhibit relatively high hardness compared to pure tungsten, which is currently used as a plasma-facing material. Typical hardness values previously reported for fusion-grade tungsten at room temperature range from 6 to 8 GPa [41]. In this study, hardness values of approximately 11 GPa and 7 GPa were obtained for the MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr layers, respectively. The high hardness of these materials results from both the nanocrystalline nature of the layers and the solid-solution strengthening effect. The presence of various elements in the crystal structure of the CSAs leads to significant lattice distortions, which is one of the most important strengthening mechanisms in this class of materials [42]. Therefore, even higher hardness values have previously been reported for various BCC—CSAs fabricated using magnetron sputtering, e.g., NbMoTaW (16 GPa) [43] or WTaCrV (13 GPa) [31].

However, when comparing the hardness values of the studied materials before and after He irradiation, negligible changes induced by ion irradiation were observed. This means that the fabricated CSAs exhibit high resistance against the irradiation hardening. Although the dpa values reached during irradiation were relatively low – 1.2 dpa for MoTaTiV and 1.4 dpa for MoTaTiVZr – such effect has previously been reported for pure tungsten, even at lower dpa levels. Zhang et al. [44] reported an increase in the nanohardness of pure tungsten irradiated with He ions at room temperature up to 1.2 dpa, from 6.1 GPa to 10.6 GPa. Similarly, Minghuan et al. [45] observed significant hardening of pure W during He irradiation at room temperature. In this case, the hardness increased from approximately 6.5 GPa to 11.5 GPa in the peak area at a damage level of 0.8 dpa. A similar effect has also been observed in other works on He-ion irradiation at room or moderate temperatures [46,47]. This phenomenon is related to the high tendency of pure tungsten to form extensive irradiation defects, such as dislocation loops, even at very low damage levels, such as 0.01 dpa [8,9]. This typically leads to severe irradiation hardening and degradation of tungsten's performance, as described previously. Recent studies have demonstrated that BCC—CSAs exhibit exceptional resistance to extensive defect formation under both light and heavy ion irradiation [31,32]. For instance, El Atwani et al. [32] reported no occurrence of irradiation-induced dislocation loops in the quaternary W-Ta-Cr-V alloy under in-situ TEM irradiation up to 8 dpa (1 MeV Kr⁺ ions) at both room and elevated temperatures. This resulted in negligible irradiation hardening of the material. Similarly, high resistance against irradiation hardening has also been observed in other studies concerning the effects of irradiation on BCC—CSAs such as TiZrNbHfTa [48], MoNbTaW [49] or HfTaTiVZr [50]. This phenomenon may be attributed to the high probability of defect recombination, which arises from the similar mobilities of defects in the investigated CSAs, thereby enhancing recombination efficiency during irradiation [13]. In contrast, in pure W, interstitials exhibit significantly higher mobility compared to vacancies, resulting in a lower W-vacancy recombination rate [14].

Understating of the He accumulation in the materials dedicated for the nuclear fusion, such as plasma facing materials, is essential from the point of their application in this environment. In the case of the nuclear fusion there are two main sources of the He atoms in structural materials: (i) transmutation reactions and (ii) implantation of the highly energetic He-ions (3.5 MeV) from the DTF reaction [51]. Since He is insoluble in metals, it relatively easy forms bigger agglomerates in the forms of the He bubbles, which highly influenced the performance of the structural materials [6]. The CSA alloys analyzed in this study represent a relatively novel approach to developing radiation-resistant materials for fusion applications. However, their unique radiation-related properties, resulted from enhanced defect recombination kinetics, have recently made them a prominent research topic [2]. Previous modeling studies, as well as experimental results on FCC-type alloys, have demonstrated that resistance to the formation of extensive irradiation-induced defects in CSA alloys is closely linked to their

Fig. 7. Over-focused BF TEM micrographs of the MoTaTiV CSA after the He-irradiation with the fluence of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (a,b) and $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (c,d).

chemical complexity, which defines the lattice distortions in these materials [11,52]. However, little is known about how this influences the radiation resistance of BCC—CSAs, which, due to the presence of high-melting-point elements such as W and Ta, appear to be particularly promising for fusion applications. Therefore, in this study, two new CSA-type alloys exhibiting significant differences in chemical complexity - MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr - were synthesized to evaluate its impact on radiation resistance in this class of alloys.

The obtained experimental data indicate that increasing chemical complexity in the studied alloys leads to the formation of smaller He bubbles under the same implantation conditions. Despite a slightly different defect accumulation mechanism associated with varying structures of the fabricated materials, the bubbles observed in the MoTaTiV alloy, which exhibited a lower degree of lattice distortion, were slightly larger than those in the MoTaTiVZr alloy. For instance, the average size of the bubbles reached $0.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$ for MoTaTiV and $0.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ nm}$ for MoTaTiVZr at a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. It should be noted that, due to the columnar microstructure of the MoTaTiV alloy at the initial phase of implantation ($1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), bubbles were mainly observed at column boundaries, which are preferential sites for their nucleation – Fig. 7. However, even considering this, with increasing He

ion fluence to $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, He bubbles within the matrix grew more rapidly than in the MoTaTiVZr alloy, which lacks preferential sites for bubble growth. In both of the analyzed materials, the bubbles formed under irradiation exhibited nanometric sizes. This is an important conclusion, as the formation of large He bubbles typically leads to material swelling [53]. It should be noted that in this study the implantation was carried out at room temperature, where both defect diffusion and He atom diffusion within the material's structure are limited [18]. Nevertheless, larger bubbles have typically been reported in pure tungsten in previous studies. For example, bubbles with sizes in the range of 1–2 nm were observed following He irradiation at temperatures below 773 K [54]. Room-temperature He irradiation of FCC—CSAs typically also results in the formation of larger bubbles; for example, bubbles ranging from 1 to 2 nm have been observed in the CoCrFeNi FCC—CSA [55]. In the case of BCC—CSAs, bubbles with an average size of approximately 2.5 nm were observed after room-temperature He irradiation in magnetron-sputtered AlCoCrFeNi [56]. Studies on the HT irradiation behavior of BCC—CSAs also indicate enhanced resistance to the formation of larger bubbles at elevated temperatures [57–59]. For instance, the formation of fine He bubbles, with sizes in the range of 2–3 nm, was observed in magnetron-sputtered WTaCrV CSA after in-situ

Fig. 8. Over-focused BF TEM micrographs of the MoTaTiVZr CSA after the He-irradiation with the fluence of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (a,b) and $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (c,d).

Table 3

Average He-bubbles size in the investigated materials.

Fluence	Average He-bubble size	
	MoTaTiV	MoTaTiVZr
$1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	$0.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$	$0.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ nm}$
$5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	$0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$	$0.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$

TEM He irradiation at 1223 K [58]. A similar effect was also observed, among others, in BCC-structured TiVNbTa irradiated with He at 973 K [60]. A low tendency for the agglomeration of He bubbles was observed in the equimolar WTaCrV alloy up to 1273 K [57]. In this case, the low diffusivity of vacancy-He clusters was found to be responsible for the high thermal stability of the bubbles. Enhanced resistance to fuzz structure formation was observed in nanocrystalline CrMoTaWV refractory CSA, attributed to reduced He diffusion compared to pure W at 1270 K. In this case, the onset of fuzz formation in CrMoTaWV occurred at a He fluence 20 times higher than that required for pure W [59]. This exceptional resistance of BCC—CSAs to He-induced defect accumulation is attributed to the overall lower diffusivity of both vacancies and He

atoms in the crystal structure of CSAs compared to pure tungsten [58].

5. Summary

In the present article, two new equimolar refractory concentrated solid solution alloys – MoTaTiV and MoTaTiVZr – were fabricated using the magnetron sputtering technique. The MoTaTiV CSA exhibited a columnar microstructure characteristic of magnetron-sputtered materials and a single-phase BCC structure. The addition of Zr to form the quinary MoTaTiVZr alloy resulted in an amorphous structure due to the significant lattice distortion introduced by the presence of Zr in the crystal structure of the material. The microstructure of the material significantly influenced the accumulation of He atoms. In the case of the MoTaTiV, the column boundaries served as preferential sites for nucleation, forming a channel along these boundaries. In contrast, in the MoTaTiVZr alloy, due to the lack of such sites, the bubbles were randomly distributed within the matrix. Despite this, it was observed that bubbles in MoTaTiV grew slightly faster than in MoTaTiVZr, indicating that increasing chemical complexity inhibits bubble growth. Nanomechanical studies also revealed no irradiation hardening, suggesting a high radiation resistance of both newly developed CSA alloys.

Fig. 9. BF/TEM micrographs of the He-irradiated ($5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) MoTaTiV (a) and MoTaTiVZr (b) layers, with the corresponding SAED patterns (c,d).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Damian Kalita: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Katarzyna Mulewska:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Iwona Jóźwik:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Yanwen Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Łukasz Kurpaska:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Philip D. Rack:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **William J. Weber:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jacek Jagielski:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research was financially supported by the National Science Centre, Poland under the SONATA 19 grant No 2023/51/D/ST11/00288. Research was funded through the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 857470 and from the European Regional Development Fund under the program of the Foundation for Polish Science International Research Agenda PLUS, grant No MAB PLUS/2018/8, and the initiative of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education 'Support for the activities of Centers of Excellence established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 program' under agreement No MEiN/2023/DIR/3795. YZ is supported through the CANADA EXCELLENCE RESEARCH CHAIRS (CERC) program. PDR acknowledge support by the National Science Foundation Materials Research Science and Engineering Center program through the UT Knoxville Center for Advanced Materials and Manufacturing (DMR-2309083). Activities financed within the framework of the undertaking of the Ministry of Education and Science entitled "Technical Description of the Research High-Temperature Gas Cooled Reactor (HTGR)" in the years 2021–2024.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] V. Philipps, Tungsten as material for plasma-facing components in fusion devices, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 415 (1) (2011) S2–S9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2011.01.110>.
- [2] X. Wang, H. Huang, J. Shi, H.-Y. Xu, D.-Q. Meng, Recent progress of tungsten-based high-entropy alloys in nuclear fusion, *Tungsten* 3 (2021) 143–160, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42864-021-00092-8>.
- [3] Z. Cheng, J. Sun, X. Gao, Y. Wang, J. Cui, T. Wang, H. Chang, Irradiation effects in high-entropy alloys and their applications, *J. Alloys Compd.* 930 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2022.166768>.
- [4] D.B. Miracle, O.N. Senkov, A critical review of high entropy alloys and related concepts, *Acta Mater.* 122 (2017) 448–511, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2016.08.081>.
- [5] P. Sharma, V.K. Dwivedi, S. Prakash, Development of high entropy alloys: a review, *Mater. Today Proc.* 43 (2021) 502–509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.12.023>.
- [6] J. Linke, J. Du, T. Loewenhoff, G. Pintsuk, B. Spilker, I. Stuedel, M. Wirtz, Challenges for plasma-facing components in nuclear fusion, *Mater. Radiat. Extrem.* 4 (2019) 56201, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5090100>.
- [7] X. Hu, T. Koyanagi, M. Fukuda, N.A.P.K. Kumar, L.L. Snead, B.D. Wirth, Y. Katoh, Irradiation hardening of pure tungsten exposed to neutron irradiation, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 480 (2016) 235–243, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2016.08.024>.
- [8] W. Chrominski, L. Ciupinski, P. Bazarnik, S. Markelj, T. Schwarz-Selinger, TEM investigation of the influence of dose rate on radiation damage and deuterium retention in tungsten, *Mater. Charact.* 154 (2019) 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2019.05.028>.
- [9] X. Yi, M.L. Jenkins, M.A. Kirk, Z. Zhou, S.G. Roberts, In-situ TEM studies of 150 keV W⁺ ion irradiated W and W-alloys: damage production and microstructural evolution, *Acta Mater.* 112 (2016) 105–120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2016.03.051>.
- [10] H. Bolt, V. Barabash, W. Krauss, J. Linke, R. Neu, S. Suzuki, N. Yoshida, A.U. Team, Materials for the plasma-facing components of fusion reactors, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 329–333 (1–3) (2004) 66–73, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2004.04.005>.
- [11] Y. Zhang, Y.N. Osetsky, W.J. Weber, Tunable chemical disorder in concentrated alloys: defect physics and radiation performance, *Chem. Rev.* 122 (1) (2022) 789–829, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00387>.
- [12] C. Lu, L. Niu, N. Chen, K. Jin, T. Yang, P. Xiu, Y. Zhang, F. Gao, H. Bei, S. Shi, M. R. He, I.M. Robertson, W.J. Weber, L. Wang, Enhancing radiation tolerance by controlling defect mobility and migration pathways in multicomponent single-phase alloys, *Nat. Commun.* 7 (2016) 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13564>.
- [13] S. Zhao, Defect properties in a VTaCrW equiatomic high entropy alloy (HEA) with the body centered cubic (bcc) structure, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 44 (2020) 133–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2019.10.025>.
- [14] J. Byggmästar, K. Nordlund, F. Djurabekova, Modeling refractory high-entropy alloys with efficient machine-learned interatomic potentials: defects and segregation, *Phys. Rev. B* 104 (10) (2021) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.104.104101>.
- [15] S. Kajita, W. Sakaguchi, N. Ohno, N. Yoshida, T. Saeki, Formation process of tungsten nanostructure by the exposure to helium plasma under fusion relevant plasma conditions, *Nucl. Fusion* 49 (2009) 095005, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0029-5515/49/9/095005>.
- [16] G. De Temmerman, K. Bystrov, R.P. Doerner, L. Marot, G.M. Wright, K.B. Woller, D.G. Whyte, J.J. Zielinski, Helium effects on tungsten under fusion-relevant plasma loading conditions, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 438 (2013) S78–S83, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2013.01.012>.
- [17] J.A.R. Wright, A review of late-stage tungsten fuzz growth, *Tungsten* 4 (2022) 184–193, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42864-021-00133-2>.
- [18] H. Iwakiri, K. Yasunaga, K. Morishita, N. Yoshida, Microstructure evolution in tungsten during low-energy helium ion irradiation, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 283–287 (2000) 1134–1138, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3115\(00\)00289-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3115(00)00289-0).
- [19] Y.G. Yan, D. Lu, K. Wang, Overview: recent studies of machine learning in phase prediction of high entropy alloys, *Tungsten* 5 (1) (2023) 32–49, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42864-022-00175-0>.
- [20] D. Pant, D.S. Aidhy, Unintuitive alloy strengthening by addition of weaker elements, *npj Comput. Mater.* 11 (1) (2025) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-025-01576-8>.
- [21] S. San, S. Hasan, P. Adhikari, W.Y. Ching, Designing quaternary and quinary refractory-based high-entropy alloys: statistical analysis of their lattice distortion, mechanical, and thermal properties, *Metals* 13 (12) (2023) 1953, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13121953> (Basel).
- [22] Y. Zhang, C. Silva, T.G. Lach, M.A. Tunes, Y. Zhou, L. Nuckols, W.L. Boldman, P. D. Rack, S.E. Donnelly, L. Jiang, L. Wang, W.J. Weber, Role of electronic energy loss on defect production and interface stability: comparison between ceramic materials and high-entropy alloys, *Curr. Opin. Solid State Mater. Sci.* 26 (4) (2022) 101001, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cossms.2022.101001>.
- [23] J.F. Ziegler, M.D. Ziegler, J.P. Biersack, SRIM – The stopping and range of ions in matter (2010), *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B Beam Interact. Mater. Atoms* 268 (2010) 1818–1823, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2010.02.091>.
- [24] A.Y. Konobeyev, U. Fischer, Y.A. Korovin, S.P. Simakov, Evaluation of effective threshold displacement energies and other data required for the calculation of advanced atomic displacement cross-sections, *Nucl. Energy Technol.* 3 (3) (2017) 169–175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NUCET.2017.08.007>.
- [25] W.C. Oliver, G.M. Pharr, An improved technique for determining hardness and elastic modulus using load and displacement sensing indentation experiments, *J. Mater. Res.* 7 (1992) 1564–1583, <https://doi.org/10.1557/JMR.1992.1564>.
- [26] G. Yetik, A. Troglia, S. Farokhipoor, S. van Vliet, J. Momand, B.J. Kooi, R. Bliem, J. W.M. Frenken, Ultrathin, sputter-deposited, amorphous alloy films of ruthenium and molybdenum, *Surf. Coatings Technol.* 445 (2022) 128729, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2022.128729>.
- [27] T. Nagase, Y. Umakoshi, Electron irradiation induced crystallization of the amorphous phase in Zr-Cu based metallic glasses with various thermal stability, *Mater. Trans.* 45 (1) (2004) 13–23, <https://doi.org/10.2320/matertrans.45.13>.
- [28] R. Effects, *Radiation effects in solids*. 2007. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4020-5295-8.
- [29] W. Xiong, A.X.Y. Guo, S. Zhan, C.-T. Liu, J.-W. Yeh, S.C. Cao, Refractory high-entropy alloys: a focused review of preparation methods and properties, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 142 (2022) 196–215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2022.08.046>.
- [30] T.X. Li, J.W. Miao, E.Y. Guo, H. Huang, J. Wang, Y.P. Lu, T.M. Wang, Z.Q. Cao, T. J. Li, Tungsten-containing high-entropy alloys: a focused review of manufacturing routes, phase selection, mechanical properties, and irradiation resistance properties, *Tungsten* 3 (2) (2021) 181–196, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42864-021-00081-x>.
- [31] D. Kalita, I. Jóźwik, Kurpaska, Y. Zhang, K. Mulewska, W. Chrominski, J. O’Connell, Y. Ge, W.L. Boldman, P.D. Rack, Y. Wang, W.J. Weber, J. Jagielski, The microstructure and He⁺ ion irradiation behavior of novel low-activation W-Ta-Cr-V refractory high entropy alloy for nuclear applications, *Nucl. Mater. Energy* 37 (2023) 101513, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NME.2023.101513>.
- [32] O. El-Atwani, N. Li, M. Li, A. Devaraj, J.K.S. Baldwin, M.M. Schneider, D. Sobiaej, J.S. Wróbel, D. Nguyen-Manh, S.A. Maloy, E. Martinez, Outstanding radiation resistance of tungsten-based high-entropy alloys, *Sci. Adv.* 5 (3) (2019) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aav2002>.
- [33] G. Pu, K. Zhang, L. Yang, Y. Luo, S. Chen, J. Li, Y. Xue, B. Liu, H. Yang, Z. Ye, F. Gou, C. Yang, Z. Wang, Y. Wang, Irradiation-enhanced superficial modification and evolution of mechanical behavior in TaTiNbZr refractory high entropy alloy films exposed to low energy helium plasma, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 577 (2023) 154337, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JNUCMAT.2023.154337>.
- [34] R. Emery, S.B. Pupilampu, A. Wood, D. Penumadu, E.A. Lass, J. Lasseter, K. A. Unocic, S. Chen, Y. Zhao, S.J. Zinkle, T. Liang, H. Xu, D.A. Gilbert, C. C. Buchanan, P.K. Liaw, P.D. Rack, Thin film combinatorial sputtering of TaTiHfZr refractory compositionally complex alloys for rapid materials discovery, *Mater. Res.* 250 (2025) 113643, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.113643>.
- [35] S. Guo, C.T. Liu, Phase stability in high entropy alloys: formation of solid-solution phase or amorphous phase, *Prog. Nat. Sci. Mater. Int.* 21 (6) (2011) 433–446, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0071\(12\)60080-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0071(12)60080-X).
- [36] S. Guo, Q. Hu, C. Ng, C.T. Liu, More than entropy in high-entropy alloys: forming solid solutions or amorphous phase, *Intermetallics* 41 (2013) 96–103, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intermet.2013.05.002>.
- [37] M.A. Tunes, H.T. Vo, J.K.S. Baldwin, T.A. Saleh, S.J. Fensin, O. El-Atwani, Perspectives on novel refractory amorphous high-entropy alloys in extreme environments, *Appl. Mater. Today* 32 (2023) 101796, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APMT.2023.101796>.
- [38] R.M. Williams, A.P. Thakoor, S.K. Khanna, W.L. Johnson, Corrosion behavior of magnetron sputter-deposited [Mo_{0.8}Ru_{0.4}]₈₂B₁₈ and Mo₈₂B₁₈ Amorphous Metal Films, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 131 (12) (1984) 2791–2794, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2115409>.
- [39] K. Mulewska, F.J. Dominguez-Gutierrez, D. Kalita, J. Byggmästar, G.Y. Wei, W. Chrominski, S. Papanikolaou, M.J. Alava, L. Kurpaska, J. Jagielski, Self-ion irradiation of high purity iron: unveiling plasticity mechanisms through nanoindentation experiments and large-scale atomistic simulations, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 586 (2023) 154690, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2023.154690>.
- [40] K. Mulewska, F. Rovaris, F.J. Dominguez-Gutierrez, W.Y. Huo, D. Kalita, I. Jozwik, S. Papanikolaou, M.J. Alava, L. Kurpaska, J. Jagielski, Self-ion irradiation effects on nanoindentation-induced plasticity of crystalline iron: a joint experimental and computational study, *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B Beam Interact. Mater. Atoms* 539 (2023) 55–61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NIMB.2023.03.004>.
- [41] L. Tanure, A. Bakaeva, A. Dubinko, D. Terentyev, K. Verbeke, Effect of annealing on microstructure, texture and hardness of ITER-specification tungsten analyzed by EBSD, vickers micro-hardness and nano-indentation techniques, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 524 (2019) 191–199, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JNUCMAT.2019.07.005>.
- [42] E.P. George, W.A. Curtin, C.C. Tasan, High entropy alloys: a focused review of mechanical properties and deformation mechanisms, *Acta Mater.* 188 (2020) 435–474, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACTAMAT.2019.12.015>.
- [43] X.B. Feng, J.Y. Zhang, Y.Q. Wang, Z.Q. Hou, K. Wu, G. Liu, J. Sun, Size effects on the mechanical properties of nanocrystalline NbMoTaW refractory high entropy alloy thin films, *Int. J. Plast.* 95 (2017) 264–277, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJPLAS.2017.04.013>.
- [44] H. Zhang, X. Zhang, Y. Li, P. Wang, L. Qiao, Effects of deuterium plasma exposure and helium ions irradiation on nanoindentation hardness of tungsten, *Nucl. Mater. Energy* 40 (2024) 101722, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NME.2024.101722>.
- [45] C. Minghuan, S. Tielong, P. Lilong, Z. Yabin, J. Peng, L. Chao, F. Xuesong, W. Zhiguang, He ion implantation induced He bubbles and hardness in tungsten, *Nucl. Mater. Energy* 15 (2018) 232–236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2018.05.004>.
- [46] C.E. Beck, S.G. Roberts, P.D. Edmondson, E.J. Armstrong, Effect of alloy composition & helium ion-irradiation on the mechanical properties of tungsten,

- tungsten-tantalum & tungsten-rhenium for fusion power applications, MRS Online Proceed. Libr. 1514 (2013) 99, <https://doi.org/10.1557/opl.2013.356>.
- [47] C.E. Beck, F. Hofmann, J.K. Eliason, A.A. Maznev, K.A. Nelson, D.E.J. Armstrong, Correcting for contact area changes in nanoindentation using surface acoustic waves, *Scr. Mater.* 128 (2017) 83–86, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.SCRIPAMAT.2016.09.037>.
- [48] M. Moschetti, A. Xu, B. Schuh, A. Hohenwarther, J.P. Couzinié, J.J. Kruzic, D. Bhattacharyya, B. Gludovatz, On the room-temperature mechanical properties of an ion-irradiated TiZrNbHfTa refractory high entropy alloy, *Jom* 72 (1) (2020) 130–138, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-019-03861-6>.
- [49] Y. Zong, N. Hashimoto, H. Oka, Study on irradiation effects of refractory bcc high-entropy alloy, *Nucl. Mater. Energy* 31 (2022) 101158, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2022.101158>.
- [50] M. Sadeghilaridjani, A. Ayyagari, S. Muskeri, V. Hasannaemi, R. Salloom, W. Y. Chen, S. Mukherjee, Ion irradiation response and mechanical behavior of reduced activity high entropy alloy, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 529 (2020) 151955, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2019.151955>.
- [51] J. Knaster, A. Moeslang, T. Muroga, Materials research for fusion, *Nat. Phys.* 12 (5) (2016) 424–434, <https://doi.org/10.1038/NPHYS3735>.
- [52] Y. Zhang, X. Wang, Y.N. Osetsky, Y. Tong, R. Harrison, S.E. Donnelly, D. Chen, Y. Wang, H. Bei, B.C. Sales, K.L. More, P. Xiu, L. Wang, W.J. Weber, Effects of 3d electron configurations on helium bubble formation and void swelling in concentrated solid-solution alloys, *Acta Mater.* 181 (2019) 519–529, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2019.10.013>.
- [53] S.J. Zinkle, G.S. Was, Materials challenges in nuclear energy, *Acta Mater.* 61 (3) (2013) 735–758, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ACTAMAT.2012.11.004>.
- [54] M. Miyamoto, S. Mikami, H. Nagashima, N. Iijima, D. Nishijima, R.P. Doerner, N. Yoshida, H. Watanabe, Y. Ueda, A. Sagara, Systematic investigation of the formation behavior of helium bubbles in tungsten, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 463 (2015) 333–336, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JNUCMAT.2014.10.098>.
- [55] R.W. Harrison, G. Greaves, H. Le, H. Bei, Y. Zhang, S.E. Donnelly, Chemical effects on He bubble superlattice formation in high entropy alloys, *Curr. Opin. Solid State Mater. Sci.* 23 (3) (2019) 100762, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cossms.2019.07.001>.
- [56] G. Pu, L. Lin, R. Ang, K. Zhang, B.B. Liu, B.B. Liu, T. Peng, S. Liu, Q. Li, Outstanding radiation tolerance and mechanical behavior in ultra-fine nanocrystalline Al_{1.5}CoCrFeNi high entropy alloy films under He ion irradiation, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 516 (2020) 146129, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.146129>.
- [57] D. Kalita, A. Esfandiarpour, I. Jóźwik, Y. Zhang, J. Byggmästar, M.J. Alava, Ł. Kurpaska, W.J. Weber, P.D. Rack, J. Jagielski, High temperature He bubble evolution and thermal stability of the WTaCrV refractory concentrated solid solution alloy, *Mater. Des.* (2025) 113751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MATDES.2025.113751>.
- [58] O. El-Atwani, A. Alvarado, K. Unal, S. Fensin, J.A. Hinks, G. Greaves, J.K. S. Baldwin, S.A. Maloy, E. Martinez, Helium implantation damage resistance in nanocrystalline W-Ta-V-Cr high entropy alloys, *Mater. Today Energy* 19 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtener.2020.100599>.
- [59] T. Cheng, G. Wei, S. Jiang, J. Zhang, Y. Wang, P. Liu, M. Hong, E. Guo, F. Zhong, G. Cai, C. Jiang, F. Ren, Enhanced resistance to helium irradiations through unusual interaction between high-entropy-alloy and helium, *Acta Mater.* 248 (2023) 118765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACTAMAT.2023.118765>.
- [60] N. Jia, Y. Li, H. Huang, S. Chen, D. Li, Y. Dou, X. He, W. Yang, Y. Xue, K. Jin, Helium bubble formation in refractory single-phase concentrated solid solution alloys under MeV He ion irradiation, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 550 (2021) 152937, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JNUCMAT.2021.152937>.